

Poddar, D. & Das, N., 2024. "World Food India 2024: Innovating for Food Security, Safety, and Sustainability" *Food Systems Insight*; 1(1): 2, pp. 1–4. DOI: <https://10.5281/zenodo.13996339>

World Food India 2024: Innovating for Food Security, Safety, and Sustainability

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Abstract . The 2024 World Food India (WFI) event, held in New Delhi and inaugurated by Prime Minister Narendra Modi, brought together global leaders in food processing to address pressing challenges related to food security, safety, and sustainability. This landmark event emphasized India's aim to emerge as a central hub for food processing innovation. Modi's inaugural address underscored the importance of combining traditional food preservation methods, such as fermentation and drying, with modern science to extend shelf life and combat food waste. Key discussions at WFI centered on advanced food preservation techniques like high-pressure processing and pulsed electric fields, both crucial for extending freshness and reducing spoilage.

Food safety and transparency took center stage, with insights into the potential of DNA-based pathogen detection and blockchain for improved traceability across the food supply chain. Technological advancements in AI and IoT also emerged as transformative tools, optimizing quality control and operational efficiency in food processing. Sustainability, a core focus at WFI, highlighted circular economy practices, bio-based packaging, water conservation, and biofuel production from food by-products, all designed to minimize environmental impact.

World Food India 2024 provided a comprehensive vision for building resilient, sustainable food systems that blend tradition with innovation, setting a global standard for food security and safety. The event's outcomes underline India's commitment to accessible, safe, and sustainable food solutions for the future.

Introduction:

The 2024 edition of World Food India (WFI), held in New Delhi, gathers global leaders in food processing to address the urgent challenges of food security, safety, and sustainability. Inaugurated by Prime Minister Narendra Modi, the event highlights India's ambitions to become a leading hub for food processing. Modi's opening remarks emphasized the need for innovative, resilient food systems built on a foundation of tradition and modern science. This piece explores the major themes discussed at WFI 2024, including food preservation, safety protocols, technological advancements, and sustainable practices.

Inauguration and 2024 Vision: A Call for Innovation

In his inaugural speech, Prime Minister Modi highlighted India's commitment to innovation in food processing, stressing the importance of blending traditional preservation techniques with modern scientific methods. Modi's address highlighted that India's rich history in food preservation—from fermentation to drying—can be enhanced by recent advancements to help tackle food waste, hunger, and economic opportunities. His call to action set the stage for WFI 2024's mission to ensure safe, sustainable food access across the globe.

Extending Shelf Life: Merging Traditional Techniques with Modern Science

One of the central focuses at WFI 2024 is reducing food waste by extending the shelf life of perishable foods. Traditional methods like fermentation, drying, and pickling—rooted in Indian culture—

have long preserved food while enhancing nutritional value. At WFI, scientists discussed combining these methods with contemporary preservation technologies to scale their benefits for larger populations.

High-pressure processing (HPP) and pulsed electric fields (PEF) are two such non-thermal technologies gaining attention. HPP utilizes high pressure to eliminate pathogens while retaining nutrients, making it suitable for products like juices and ready-to-eat meals. PEF, on the other hand, uses electric fields to achieve similar results in a non-destructive way, extending product shelf life without compromising on quality or safety. These methods are particularly valuable for areas with limited refrigeration facilities, offering a safe and energy-efficient solution to extend food freshness.

Biopreservatives, another modern advancement, were highlighted for their potential in naturally preserving food. Derived from plants or microbial cultures, biopreservatives inhibit the growth of harmful bacteria, extending food shelf life without the need for synthetic additives. This approach offers a more sustainable and consumer-friendly option for food preservation, supporting the event's focus on safe, accessible food options.

Building Consumer Trust: Enhancing Food Safety and Transparency

Food safety is essential for building consumer confidence in processed foods. At WFI 2024, experts emphasized the role of rigorous safety protocols and transparency in food processing. The use of DNA-based pathogen detection systems represents a significant leap in ensuring food safety across the production chain. Capable of

detecting pathogens like E. coli and Salmonella with precision, these systems enable swift action to prevent contamination, which is vital in today's interconnected global market.

Blockchain technology was another focus, highlighted for its ability to enhance traceability and transparency in the supply chain. This technology stores all supply chain data in a secure digital ledger, providing consumers with accurate information about a product's journey from farm to table. Blockchain's transparency helps prevent food fraud and adulteration, supporting consumer trust in food safety.

Technological Innovation: AI and IoT in Food Processing

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT) in food processing was a prominent theme at WFI 2024. These technologies enhance both quality control and resource efficiency. For instance, IoT sensors monitor critical variables like temperature and humidity in real-time, allowing for precise quality control at every stage. Additionally, AI algorithms support predictive maintenance in processing plants, analyzing data patterns to forecast potential equipment issues. This helps prevent downtime and improves operational efficiency, both crucial for high-volume food processing.

Automation, specifically through robotics, is transforming repetitive tasks in food processing. Automated systems handle sorting, grading, and packaging with precision, improving product uniformity and safety. This shift to automation not only increases productivity but also reduces resource

use and costs, positioning food processing plants to scale operations sustainably.

Sustainability in Food Processing: Circular Practices and Reduced Resource Consumption

Sustainability was a core theme at WFI 2024, with an emphasis on circular economy practices that reduce environmental impact and waste. As the food industry is responsible for significant greenhouse gas emissions, the need for sustainable practices is urgent. At WFI, attendees explored bio-based packaging materials made from agricultural by-products as an alternative to plastic. These biodegradable options reduce landfill waste and align with environmental goals.

The event also highlighted efforts to reduce water and energy consumption. Advanced drying technologies use less heat, reducing energy demands and preserving the moisture content and quality of foods. Water recycling systems in food plants further contribute to sustainability by purifying and reusing water, significantly lowering the water footprint of food production. These sustainable solutions align with WFI's vision of balancing economic growth with environmental responsibility.

Repurposing food by-products was another area of innovation, with solutions such as converting vegetable residues into biofuels or using fruit peels in bio-packaging. These approaches create value from food waste, supporting a circular economy model where resources are reused rather than discarded.

Conclusion

World Food India 2024 emphasizes a comprehensive approach to food processing, blending traditional knowledge with modern scientific advancements to build resilient, sustainable food systems. From advanced preservation techniques and rigorous safety protocols to data-driven automation and sustainable practices, the industry is evolving to meet global food challenges. The vision set forth at WFI 2024 demonstrates a commitment to ensuring that safe, sustainable food options are accessible to everyone, fostering a future where food security is within reach.

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Competing Interests

The author declares that they have no competing interests.

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